

The Effects of Learning Medium on Student Perceptions

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic affected many aspects of people's lives, especially education. Health concerns made regular face-to-face classes difficult. There were higher levels of stress for students in online classes (Chung, 2021, paras. 4-8). Some schools experienced difficulties with online classes- so much so that the students returned to the campus for face-to-face classes in the next school year (Travis, 2021). Other schools, however, found great success for students and teachers through online classes and remained in the medium for the next school year (Chaturvedi, 2021). Decisions on keeping or removing online classes varied from district to district. The experiences of the students in both mediums played a significant role in this decision-making.

The COVID-19 pandemic period referred to the 2020 through 2021 school year in this study. Learning medium referred to a format through which students are educated. High school level classes referred to classes that were taken in high school by students in grades 9 through 12. College level classes were taken by graduate or undergraduate students at universities and colleges, which varied for each previous study. This study explored high school level classes. Online classes, online learning environment, online course, and digital classroom were all synonymous terms for college or high school level classes that took place with live online instruction (synchronous) or without (asynchronous) in a digital format, such as a website or application (Tidwell, Southard, & Mooney, 2010). The online classes in this study specifically were run through Zoom video calls and a student portal, where students could access and work on assignments and tests. Face-to-face classes/courses and the traditional classroom referred to college or highschool level classes that took place at campus where both teachers and students

were present in the same room. Student perceptions referred to perceived accessibility, attitude toward the course, perceived level of social interaction, the ability of the course to match expectations, and perceived usefulness (Landrum, 2020). Perceptions are different from student satisfaction because they also observe perceptions of class structure through data on perceived accessibility. Some may assume that cheating was more prominent in online classes because of their remote nature. However, cheating was equally as likely to occur through either medium (in college level classes), even though students believed it was easier to cheat in online classes (Miller & Young-Jones, 2012). However, students who only took online classes were also more mature and therefore were less prone to cheating than face-to-face students.

In the 2021 through 2022 school year, a school district in Frisco, Texas had both online and face-to-face options for school after the first 6 weeks of school being online only. Students had a variety of experiences in that year because they were given the ability to choose their learning medium after trying face-to-face school. I wanted to explore students' perceptions of both mediums during this year through a qualitative evaluative method.

The goal of this study was to evaluate the extent to which medium of learning (online versus face to face) affected student perceptions of school in terms of their qualitative responses for 9th and 10th graders at XYZ district in the 2020 through 2021 school year. This information helped determine what aspects of both mediums were good and bad, which can be applied to improve the quality of both mediums or use the best aspects of both to make a system that works better for students.

Literature Review

Online courses proliferated in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic period, because of which many schools had a general dissatisfaction with the disorganized atmosphere of online classes, which included technical difficulties and inaccessibility; there was generally less instructor interaction in online courses compared to face-to-face classes, which was a primary concern for many students, as they missed the “eye contact, body language, and voice tones” (Serhan, 2010, pp. 23) that made up a student-teacher relationship.

There was also a learning medium between the two: hybrid classes. These included courses that conduct anywhere from 31% to 79% of the class online (Tidwell, Southard, & Mooney, 2010, pp. 72).

Teachers & Educators

Todd Zipper, the president of an academic program management company called Wiley Education Services, expressed how hybrid classes can be advantageous to more students. He believed that “instead of approaching education from a ‘this or that’ approach, we’d serve students much better with a ‘this and that’ approach” (Zipper, 2020) because it caters to the needs of more students by providing both accessibility and instructor interaction.

Considering recent improvements in technology and online class format, many chief academic officers, or deans, perceived online classes as “good as or better than face-to-face [classes]” (Allen & Seaman, 2013, pp. 5), but a constant minority of them believed that online classes were mediocre in comparison to face-to-face classes.

Social media usage during classwork time was at times a major concern, as it led to a decrease in communication skills (Williams, 2021). Smith, Ferguson, and Caris, however, argue that online classes have allowed shy or quiet students to participate in activities openly without social anxiety (2001).

Regardless, teachers valued face-to-face classes over online classes because of the physical presence of students and teachers at one location (Kosar, 2021).

Academic Performance

In terms of academic performances, specifically on final exam scores, many studies showed that academic performance did not differ greatly between the learning mediums (Shachar & Neumann, 2003, Stack, 2021, Driscoll et al., 2012, Wachenheim, 2008).

In contrast, many other studies argued that students generally tended to score higher on exams than face-to-face students (Sims & Schulman, 1999, Hart, Berger, Jacob, Loeb, & Bill 2019).

A factor that might account for this discrepancy is cheating (Miller & Young-Jones, 2012). This may cause the average scores in one medium to be higher than the other and make the measurement of academic performance inaccurate.

Student Perceptions

Examining Students' Confidence to Learn Online, Self-Regulation Skills and Perceptions of Satisfaction and Usefulness of Online Classes by Brittany Landrum (2020), who is an assistant professor of the Technology & Education Department at the University of Dallas, observed how factors like confidence and self-regulation affected their perceptions of satisfaction

and usefulness of the online class. Landrum reached the conclusion that the more confidence and self-regulation a student had, the better their perceptions of satisfaction with the online course.

Exploring Egyptian EFL Students' Learning Styles and Satisfaction with Web-Based Materials by Ahmed Mahmoud Aliweh (2011), who is a professor in the Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) Department of Learning and Instruction and faculty of Education at Tanta University, examined how students' learning styles influenced their satisfaction with an online course. This study discovered that tactile, kinesthetic, and visual learners were more prominent in online courses, although the limited sample size of 51 third-year college students may not reflect the primary learning styles of a large population of online learners.

Student perceptions of online versus on campus instruction by Lawrence A. Beard and Cynthia Harper discussed "student attitudes and opinions towards online course instruction" (2002). Many students would take another online course, but would also prefer instructor and peer interaction. In addition, there were technical difficulties that negatively affected students' perceptions

Landrum's study and Aliweh's study observed the effects of two different variables on student satisfaction in online classes. Landrum evaluates the extent to which confidence and self-regulation impacted satisfaction, whereas Aliweh explores the dominance of certain traits in online course students. Both agreed that there were a lot of positive perceptions associated with the online medium. Conversely, Beard and Harper discovered many issues that students faced and how they created a more negative attitude towards online courses. However, the students in their study would still take another online course, so the ideas expressed by Landrum and Aliweh carried weight.

During the COVID-19 pandemic period, multiple studies were conducted to understand student perceptions of online courses. Many of the studies described how much students like or disliked the online format. They did not compare the perceptions to those of face-to-face classes, which suggests that they ignored them or that they might have assumed that students had great, ideal perceptions of face-to-face classes which may not be true. Unlike studies that compared academic performance in both mediums, these studies explored the positive and negative aspects in online courses while not acknowledging the presence or lack thereof of those aspects in face-to-face courses. Although Landrum's study actually compared student perceptions of the two mediums, its sample was college students in college classes, so there was no gap at the college level. Regardless, there was no juxtaposition between online and face-to-face classes at the high school level during the COVID-19 pandemic period. The juxtaposition in this study showed the differences and similarities between the two and framed the discussion.

Method

Design

The design of the study was exploratory and non-experimental because no treatments were imposed. The design was exploratory because the parts of both mediums that were significant to the subjects were not clear from previous studies, given the gap at the high school level. This design fit into the Body of Knowledge because it had a qualitative exploratory design similar to that of a study conducted with 41 undergraduate students in hybrid and online classes (El Mansour, 2007). This design juxtaposed learning mediums to provide a cohesive understanding of them through students' perspectives. This design was valid because it had clear

questions that brought up valuable answers that addressed the research question, but at the same time, how the research question was addressed was open to each subject because of the exploratory nature. Basically, the questions guided students just enough to where the response structure was left open to interpretation.

Qualitative Evaluative Method

The evaluative method took qualitative open-ended responses and helped find ideas that were common trends across responses. This method fit into the research design because the ultimate purpose of this study was to know how students really felt about both learning mediums through their perceptions. The qualitative method was the ultimate choice because the lack of structure was what allowed the subjects to express their perspectives best. Multiple choice questions or ratings do not provide the liberty of expression that qualitative responses do. This free response aspect was important because this method was meant to *explore* students' perceptions of both mediums. The topics that might have been relevant to students were, to an extent, unclear, which was why this study was designed to be exploratory. This was also another reason why it was difficult to define close-ended questions.

Subjects & Confidentiality

The subjects of the study are current sophomores and juniors, or in other words, students that were freshmen and sophomores in the 2020 through 2021 school year in a school district in Frisco. These subjects were ideal candidates to address the research question because they were required to experience online school. Not all students took face-to-face classes, though, but there was still a significant number of students that did take classes face-to-face. Not only this, but students were given the option to switch between both mediums periodically throughout the year.

Additionally, there was a firm reason to stratify the data by grade level. Current 11th grade students started high school face-to-face with regular school in their freshmen year, so face-to-face classes were their first high school experience (as their baseline). In contrast, current 10th grade students started high school with their first 6 weeks of school required to be online. Their first high school medium changed what their personal baseline was, which explains how this affected their perception of the other medium. No personally identifying information was collected from the subjects other than their grade level.

The subjects of the study filled out consent forms in September of 2021 through their AP Seminar and AP Research teachers, approved with their parents' signatures. Parents and students were fully informed of the consent process. In order to preserve the confidentiality of data, this survey is entirely anonymous except for the students' grade levels. Additionally, the data was stored in a google sheets document, which is soundly secured by Google. The data collected was not accessible to anyone other than myself. This study was approved by the IRB committee to carry out the data collection.

Instruments

One google form survey instrument was used in September of 2021 to get informed consent from all subjects. All subjects who participated in the study submitted the consent form with parent approval. It was most efficient to gain consent this way because the form was given out by AP Seminar and AP Research teachers across the district directly to their students. There was one online google form survey used to collect data. This instrument was chosen because google form surveys are easy to send to the subjects and to collect responses. Handing out and collecting physical surveys would have taken more time and resources. There were 8 open-ended

questions on the survey that assessed all important aspects of student perceptions of online and face-to-face school, with 4 questions for each medium. There were also two multiple choice questions to find out which grade subjects were in and to determine whether or not the subject can answer questions about face-to-face school, because if they were in online classes the whole year, they were only allowed to answer the online school questions. This instrument helped in gathering information on students' perceptions of both learning mediums through four qualitative ideas. Each medium had 4 questions that pertained to accessibility, social interaction, course expectations, and perceived usefulness. These factors were inspired from those studied in *Examining Students' Confidence to Learn Online, Self-Regulation Skills and Perceptions of Satisfaction and Usefulness of Online Classes* (Landrum, 2020). This was because all of these factors gave a better summation of students' experiences in both mediums. These questions addressed the research question by directly collecting information from the subjects about the perceptions of their school experiences through four discrete aspects from both mediums. This gave a well rounded idea of their perspectives and provided a straight answer to the research question. There were limitations to the validity of the instrument, since open-ended responses were not controlled and subjects could enter responses that didn't answer the question or lacked insight to their experiences. However, a factor that I believe played a strong role in improving the validity of the research was the topic of the research. Many students had a lot to express about their school experiences during online school, and so this survey was, in a way, a place for them to "rant" about the school year. Given that the topic was of interest to the subjects in this sense, they were more likely to answer the questions with time and focus, effectively increasing the validity of the instrument.

Procedure

To collect data, potential subjects were first asked to participate through my school's AP Research teacher who sent out the survey link to AP Seminar and AP Research students across the district on a google document that contained links to studies for students across the district. Students were able to participate in other students' studies across the district. Then, responses were collected during the collection window. The data collection window ended on December 17th.

Similar or repeated words and phrases across responses (within a grade level) were used to find trends. First, the data was separated by grade. Then, each response was analyzed to find how often specific words and phrases appeared. These words and phrases indicated an attitude toward the medium. For example, in the question asking about the accessibility of online school, multiple students specifically mentioned "connection issues" or a similar phrase with the same meaning as an accessibility issue they faced. The frequency of these words across responses was important because it allowed me to form a code. Each questions' responses led to new codes and some even connected back to previous codes. These codes were significant because they then allowed thematic analysis on the data. These codes allowed the identification of well-defined recurring themes, which were the findings of this study. This process was repeated for each question and the data from one medium was kept separate from the other medium. This was because this study was meant to analyze the differences in the perceptions of mediums with grade level as strata. These recurring ideas lead to specific findings about how students perceived each medium. This was because when a large percentage of the students in the large, random sample shared the same ideas, the population was likely to have a greater proportion of students

that also agreed with those ideas because there was little chance variation due to random assignment. All of this data was time-consuming to analyze, but the analysis process took free responses and restructured them. In this sense, open-ended responses made less sense, because the process of taking qualitative data and quantifying it seemed so unnecessary if closed-ended questions could have been used in the first place. However, considering the exploratory nature of the study, this process makes more sense and becomes necessary.

Findings & Discussion

56 responses were collected with exactly 28 responses from each grade level. 14 of the subjects also took face-to-face classes and gave responses for them. It was found that students perceived both benefits and drawbacks to both learning mediums. Online classes offered schedule flexibility at the expense of social interaction, while face-to-face classes made it easier to learn and had relatively more social interaction. Overall, subjects in face-to-face classes had better learning experiences than those in online classes (see Appendix B).

Theme	Definition	Keywords	Theme	Definition	Keywords
Ease of Time Management	Many subjects discussed the flexibility of their schedule when taking online classes. Subject 10 mentioned their "[freedom to do work whenever i wanted]" which captured this theme perfectly. The keywords associated with this theme were flexibility, free time, high accessibility, good sleep schedule, free time, ease, and useful.	Flexible	Content Comprehension Issues	This theme captured the difficulty subjects had with learning online. The majority of subjects responded that they learned little and what they had learned was inapplicable, and so the online classes were not useful. The keywords associated with this theme were difficult to learn, learned little, inapplicable knowledge, and not useful.	Difficult to learn
		Accessible			Learned little
		Better sleep schedule			Inapplicable knowledge
		Free time			Class not useful
		Easy			
		Very useful	Social Limitations	This theme referred to the limited social interaction subjects experienced in online classes. The keywords associated with this theme were collaboration issues, low social interaction, awkward/unfamiliar classmates, isolation, lack of conversation, and forced group discussion.	Collaboration issues
					Low social interaction
Accessibility Limitations	Accessibility limitations hindered a participant's ability to approach or use online classes. This theme was prominent across responses and mainly consisted of technical issues that subjects experienced. The keywords associated with this theme were connection issues, low accessibility, and communication issues.	Connection issues			Awkward or unfamiliar classmates
		Low accessibility			Isolation
		Communication issues			Lack conversation
					Forced group discussion
Stagnant Class Structure	This theme describes the issues with the class structure in terms of how class time was spent. Many subjects reported that their teachers would often just talk to students throughout the entire class. There was little back and forth interaction between student and teacher, and so the keywords associated with this theme were lack of student-teacher interaction, lecture style, and boring/unengaging.	Lack of student-teacher interaction			
		Lecture style			
		Boring/unengaging			

The table above shows the themes discovered for online classes.

Theme	Definition	Keywords
Learning Benefits	Subjects focused on how much more they were able to learn face-to-face. The keywords associated with this theme were accessible, easy to learn, very useful, learned a lot, and very applicable.	accessible/very accessible easy to learn very useful learned a lot very applicable
High Social Interaction	Compared to online classes, subjects argued that face-to-face classes offered both peer-to-peer and student-to-teacher interaction. The keywords associated with this theme were conversation, collaboration, friends, and ability to ask questions.	high social interaction conversation collaboration friends ask questions
COVID Social Restrictions	Even though there was more social interaction, there were still limitations to the face-to-face interaction due to the pandemic as described by the subjects. The keywords associated with this theme were low interaction, isolation, and social distancing.	low interaction/isolation social distancing

The table above shows the themes discovered for face-to-face classes.

Online Recurring Theme 1: Ease of Time Management

Many subjects discussed the flexibility of their schedule when taking online classes. Subject 12 mentioned that they "could work at [their] own pace" which captured this theme perfectly. The keywords associated with this theme were flexibility, free time, high accessibility, good sleep schedule, free time, ease, and usefulness. 37 of 56 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses. While many subjects found the flexibility useful and used it to better manage their time, many subjects also procrastinated and lacked the motivation to work when they were put in front of a screen. Late assignments were commonplace for these students. Overall, though, more independent time management helped more students than it harmed.

Online Recurring Theme 2: Accessibility Limitations

Accessibility limitations hindered a participant's ability to approach or use online classes. This theme was prominent across responses and mainly consisted of technical issues that subjects experienced. The keywords associated with this theme were connection issues, low accessibility, and communication issues. 28 of 56 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses. Even the students that thought online classes were accessible mentioned technical issues like Subject 46 who thought "It was pretty accessible, but because of wifi issues [they] sometimes missed parts of the lesson." This captures how accessibility limitations were one of the most recurring issues with online classes. Technical and connection issues negatively affected students' experience in online classes and fundamentally shaped their understanding of the medium.

Online Recurring Theme 3: Stagnant Class Structure

This theme describes the issues with the class structure in terms of how class time was spent. Many subjects reported that their teachers would often just talk to students throughout the entire class. There was little back and forth interaction between student and teacher, and so the keywords associated with this theme were lack of student-teacher interaction, lecture style, unengaging, and boring. 28 of 56 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses. Almost all of these subjects mentioned something along the lines of "the teacher just talked the whole time." This shows exactly why students found it difficult to stay engaged: for many classes, the teacher would lecture the class for 90 minutes nonstop. This shapes students' perceptions of online classes by associating them with boredom and a lack of engagement.

Online Recurring Theme 4: Content Comprehension Issues

This theme captured the difficulty subjects had with learning online. The majority of subjects responded that they learned little and what they had learned was inapplicable, and so the online classes were not useful. The keywords associated with this theme were difficult to learn, learned little, inapplicable knowledge, and lack of usefulness. 25 of 56 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses.

Online Recurring Theme 5: Social Interaction Limitations

This theme referred to the limited social interaction subjects experienced in online classes. The keywords associated with this theme were collaboration issues, low social interaction, awkward/unfamiliar classmates, isolation, lack of conversation, and forced group discussion. 43 of 56 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses.

Face-to-face Recurring Theme 6: Learning Benefits

Subjects focused on how much more they were able to learn face-to-face. The keywords associated with this theme were accessible, easy to learn, high usefulness, learned a lot, and very applicable. 13 of 13 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses.

Face-to-face Recurring Theme 7: High Social Interaction

Compared to online classes, subjects argued that face-to-face classes offered both peer-to-peer and student-to-teacher interaction. The keywords associated with this theme were conversation, collaboration, friends, and ability to ask questions. 12 of 13 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses. Relative to online classes, face-to-face classes provide much more social interaction including things like “being able to eat lunch with friends.” The higher social interaction in face-to-face classes made it the “winner” for the social aspect of school during that year.

Face-to-face Recurring Theme 8: COVID-19 Restrictions

Even though there was more social interaction overall, there were still limitations to face-to-face interaction due to the pandemic as described by the subjects. The keywords associated with this theme were low interaction, isolation, and social distancing. 5 of 13 responses mentioned one or more of these keywords in their responses. While there was more interaction relative to online classes, there was still significantly less interaction compared to the face-to-face classes in the previous (2019 through 2020) school year. This was a fact noted by those who went to Frisco high schools during that year and shows how face-to-face classes were not the ideal social environment, but was instead the “lesser of two evils” when it came to the level of social interaction students experienced.

Implications

This study shows that online classes in the form that was provided in XYZ district were ineffective at providing a proper educational experience to students. However, aspects of the online classes, like flexibility and ease of time management, were superior to face-to-face classes from a mental health perspective. XYZ district could use the information from this study to better support students by the introduction of a hybrid learning medium. It would take the best aspects of both mediums to create an environment that encourages interaction, education, and mental well-being. This study provides the evidence needed to bring a change that would improve the education of students across XYZ district. In addition, the results of this study both contrast and corroborate the findings of other researchers, and so it helps build arguments in the existing literature about the fundamental nature of online classes, especially because different

forms of online classes exist throughout the country, and this study provides an answer to how Zoom directed classes were perceived by students.

Limitations

One major limitation is that the scope of this study is limited to two grade levels from one school district. This means that the results of this study provide useful information on a district level but are not applicable county or state wide. Additionally, the fact that subjects volunteered to participate in the study may affect the results because they may have stronger opinions or be more open to providing information than others. For this reason, the sample may not capture a realistic distribution of the frequency of themes, although the randomization, relatively large sample size, and ten percent rule allow us to assume that the sample is a good representation of the population.

Future Suggestions

First and foremost, future studies should try to expand the scale of the study and capture data from a much larger sample over a much greater area. While this will have a smaller local impact it will provide information that can be useful to many more people than a local study. Additionally, future studies should consider addressing the question of student grade and how they relate to their perceptions of learning mediums.

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Appendix A

2/11/22, 12:06 AM

The Effects of Learning Medium on Student Perceptions

The Effects of Learning Medium on Student Perceptions

Hello! This survey wants to discover how current sophomores and juniors at Independence perceived online and face-to-face classes last year. Learning medium refers to the format through which students learned (online or face-to-face). Please avoid any personally identifying information, and fill out this survey with as much accuracy as possible. If you don't remember the exact details of something, you can specify that you "don't remember." This survey should take around 10-15 minutes.

* Required

Consent
Form

Please read this consent form:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gpjf5X8eWBXn4NUA-4oh6-hm0dbV1QQ0/edit?usp=sharing&oid=115763893110358438937&rtpof=true&sd=true>

1. Do you agree to participate in this study? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

IMPORTANT:

Please make sure your responses are developed and reflect all your experiences.

2. Current Grade Level *

Mark only one oval.

10th grade

11th grade

3. How accessible was online school? Describe the drawbacks or benefits in the accessibility of online school that you experienced (this may include technical or other issues). *

2/11/22, 12:06 AM

The Effects of Learning Medium on Student Perceptions

4. Describe how much social interaction you had in online classes. Explain your reasoning. *

5. Was online school what you expected it to be? Was it better or worse than expected and why? *

6. How useful were the online classes? How much did you learn and how applicable was that learning? *

7. Did you also take face-to-face classes last year? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Face-to-face classes

8. How accessible was face-to-face school? Describe the drawbacks or benefits in the accessibility of face-to-face school that you experienced. *

9. Describe how much social interaction you had in face-to-face classes. Explain your reasoning. *

2/11/22, 12:06 AM

The Effects of Learning Medium on Student Perceptions

10. Was face-to-face school what you expected it to be? Was it better or worse than expected and why? *

11. How useful were the face-to-face classes? How much did you learn and how applicable was that learning? *

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Google Forms

Appendix B

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
11th grade	It was ok, i got to stay at home. But content was a bit harder to learn/understand and teaching didn't really occur as worksheets were just given.	3, occasional breakout rooms, yet no one talked.	It was as expected, had some benefits but lacked teaching.	Not useful, learned minimum and don't really remember much of what i learned.
11th grade	technical issues	1 because during breakout rooms people weren't present and during class it would mainly be lectures.	worse	i learned a little
11th grade	Sometimes there were internet issues, and it was kind of hard to do work	2- we listened to the teacher and then left	It was better than I thought because it allowed for a lot of flexibility	Not at all, I learned basically nothing
10th grade	While it was easier in some cases, it wasn't engaging and I didn't learn as much. My grades would have been much better if I went face-to-face.	4-5. While it wasn't as much as face-to-face, we still needed to answer questions from the teacher and talk to other classmates.	It was worse than expected. I thought it would be easy, but because it was also the first year of high school it was very hard.	I didn't learn as much because it wasn't as engaging. I didn't really want to be in the classes and I wasn't forced to because I was at home.
10th grade	It was accessible in the sense that the content was readily available and rich in material. However, guidance in the form of actual teachers was difficult to access due to the virtual format and number of students.	My social interaction was limited to any social interactions that I had outside of school hours. We had breakout rooms, but they rarely facilitated discussion.	It was essentially how I expected it to be. It was a little worse than I expected as I didn't receive actual face to face interaction and couldn't retain much of my knowledge.	The online courses were helpful as they helped ensure I was still learning something. I didn't learn much however, and it would have been helpful if I could still remember it all now.
10th grade	Very accessible. Technical issues such as internet issues.		1 Worse it made me really stressed out and ruined my routine at school. I procrastinate way too much now.	Pretty useful. A lot and I can use it later.

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
11th grade	it was accessible for me, because i had a device that i could use to access all of my work. some benefits were that it was more convenient, i could travel while doing work, etc. some drawbacks are that i needed a personal device and constant access to wifi. on top of this, i couldn't hang out or make new friends as easily, but it was still possible to do so.		it was a bit better than i had expected, because for most classes, i could work at my own pace, resulting in higher grades.	most were useful, the only one that didn't help me was algebra 2, because it was extremely difficult for me to learn the topics.
10th grade	easily accessible not many issues	1 nobody talked except teacher	Yes it was better because I could sleep during most of it	Not very useful didnt learn much
11th grade	I did have some technical issues that impacted by ability to attend class and complete assignments. However, everything could be accessed 24/7, which was helpful.	3, I very rarely talked to anyone during class who was not my friend.	Online school was worse than expected because I underestimated how hard it is to learn solely off a computer at home all the time, with no breaks to walk around or talk to people during class.	I did not learn much during online school as it was not required to memorize any information.
11th grade	lots of technical issues	like 4 because of covid you couldn't even hang out with friends	worse	did not learn anything

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
10th grade	It was easy to connect with people and I was able to complete work faster. The technology was not always capable of supporting an entire virtual class and it was difficult if not impossible to have social interactions with peers.	1, the zoom calls were hardly social interaction as nobody spoke, and I did not connect with anybody outside of classes, I remained isolated in my own home.	It was very close to what I expected it to be, I had hoped for potentially a more welcoming environment and found it less interactive than I had expected, as many individuals did not participate in virtual activities or in virtual classes. Overall I believe that it was worse than I had expected because the zoom calls were stressful and I did not get to meet any people because it was my first year in high school.	The online classes were moderately useful for learning new material, however, I believe that I learned much more through assignment than in the actual online classes. It was not very applicable at the time because there was no way to use things that I learned without an actual classroom, but upon returning to school I realized that the online classes were not a complete waste.
10th grade	Online school was VERY difficult for many different reasons. I live in a very fortunate household, and I had many issues with online classes, the online learning environment, isolation, and even technical things such as Wifi or web crashes.		2 It was what I expected it to be. People did not communicate well because we were stuck behind our screens. Students did not learn much at all because they did not have a teacher physically there and could cheat or not complete assignments. It was bad also because people were afraid to reach out for help or ask questions to better engage.	It was not useful, and I think my learning suffered. I was having to learn everything on my own.
10th grade	it was hard to ask questions and sometimes other people and i could not be heard	4 the most i did was online calling	a little worse because I hated being mostly independent	went over important content but i did not learn as much so it was somewhat useful

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
10th grade	It was super accessible, despite some technical difficulties like Zoom shutting down or links not working.	1, even when forced to participate in breakout groups on Zoom, no one talked to each other.	No, I expected it to be good because I could get my work done faster and learn at my own pace, however it made me lonely and actually stunted my learning because I had no motivation to complete my assignment.	I think online classes are useful in some situations, when it is impossible to meet face-to-face. I hardly learned in online classes, it was hard to adjust when coming back to face-to-face school.
11th grade	There were a lot of technical issues especially during classes and while taking tests.	8 because I communicated with my friends every day.	It was better because I was able to work at my own pace.	They were not useful because the teachers were not very capable and there were a lot of technical issues.
10th grade	it allowed me to do things at my own time, but it was hard for me to have a good schedule and learn properly.	2 because zooms did not help you socialize	it was worse because it was worse because I felt like I wasn't able to experience anything	I did not effectively learn much.
10th grade	Online school was pretty accessible, I rarely had technical issues.	2	I thought I'd be really happy to have online school, being able to stay in my pajamas, eat whenever I want and be in my bed, but it was so boring and it was much worse than I expected.	I hardly learned anything and I had zero motivation to complete any work or pay attention.
11th grade	Online school was fine, but the social disconnect I had with my teachers in the learning environment really took a toll on me	4 ,, did not talk much	I used to like it a lot but then it just became a routine that I grew to hate	I really did not like online class since I could not retain any information being taught.
10th grade	Very easy to use but if one thing is not working it restricts everything	Not much, did not feel connected to anyone, awkward	It was better, because I felt a lot of pressure but it was easy, not fun though	Not helpful, hard to understand in no 1 on 1 time.

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
11th grade	I accessed it just fine, it was overall beneficial for me because I had more time to study and complete lessons at my own pace. I didn't have too many tech issues, but it was annoying when the mic or camera was on when I didn't turn it on.	Moderate to minimal, because I didn't really talk to my classmates. Most interactions consisted of groups on zoom, that's it.	It was better than expected, I still to grasp concepts- so it worked out for me.	I learned a lot quickly, but my memory on the subjects deteriorated. It's not too applicable now.
10th grade	Navigating online school was definitely a bit rocky at first, but it was very convenient and efficient to use once technical issues were resolved. It was convenient that our workplace could be at our choosing, but it was difficult to ask teachers questions at times.	I probably had social interaction with students a couple of times a month. I had social interaction with teachers several times a week.	No, it was better than expected because I had thought that navigating online platforms may be difficult and communication may be unclear, however, once the district got the hang of it, it was pretty smooth.	Online classes were very useful, however, paying attention was difficult because there are so many distractions online, such as social media.
10th grade	it was alright, too much work	A decent amount, talked to my friends	Worse, lots of work	Pretty useful, didn't really learn much
10th grade	it was very accessible	None	Worse because I did not learn much	not very useful and the learning was not very applicable
10th grade	Online school was pretty accessible. Some drawbacks included not a lot of teacher input and having to learn most of the course by yourself.	I had a decent amount of social interaction in my online classes because I actively participated in any class discussions the teacher was having. However, when it came to breakout rooms it was very awkward to communicate with other students.	Online school was worse because I was expecting it to be more asynchronous with less work and instead we had work piled up.	They weren't very useful and I didn't retain much of the information because my attention span was much lower and the learning wasn't much applicable either.

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
11th grade	For the most part I had accessibility - good laptop, phone, quiet environment, but I had wifi issues time to time	None. No one talked except the teacher in zoom classes	I thought it would be more interactive between students but it was worse than I expected because there was no aspects of socializing whatsoever.	I learned very little because I mainly just focused on getting good grades. I was not really able to understand the content from a zoom call and I felt awkward asking questions.
10th grade	GOOD	barely any	yes	not much
11th grade	drawbacks: removed from school environment, lowering motivation benefits: much more loose, wore pajamas to school	Like none, no opportunities to speak to people for fun, when in breakout rooms because of mixing of high schools conversation was often stilted and awkward and was only about classes	No - both better and worse. Better because everything was looser but I also spent a lot of wasted time.	n/a
10th grade	Online school wasn't very accessible due to internet outages.	I had quite a bit of social interaction through online platforms such as discord.	Online school was exactly what I had expected it to be.	Online school was relatively useful, because I was able to learn and had a lot more free time.
10th grade	I wasn't in online school	I wasn't in online school	I wasn't in online school	I wasn't in online school
10th grade	there were technical problems, and bad teachers	not much, because i couldn't interact outside of school work	better, because i had better grades	not much
10th grade	easy	alot	no	alot

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online school?	Describe how much social interaction you had?	Was online school what you expected?	How useful were the online classes?
10th grade	I enjoyed being able to adjust my schedule as I pleased, such as utilizing class work time for other subjects, eating whenever I wanted to, and getting to ask as many questions I needed to after class because we a lot of time left over.	I did not have much social interaction at all because I only two classes with people I mostly knew, with people I have phone numbers of. Because the high school students of FISD were so mixed up and because of the nature of zoom calls, it was very difficult to make friends or interact with people in general.	It had its pros and cons but I feel that it was better than I expected due to all of the flexibility I had with my time.	I did learn a lot because I really think I learned how to study effectively during the era of online classes. How applicable the content was depends on the course.
11th grade	The benefits of online school was that I had more time on my hands to do my assignments and it was easier completing tests without the stress. However, I couldn't meet with my friends or interact with my teacher as much as I would've liked.	Not much. It was hard talking to people on zoom in the classes.	It was the way I expected it to be. I had a lot of time to do my assignments, but not much social interaction.	I didn't learn as much I would've in normal school. For example, we didn't do many of the science labs as it required in person school to do so.
10th grade	Very accessible. 0 drawbacks	I was on calls with my friends so I had good social interaction.	Online school was really stressful and relaxed.	I didn't learn anything from the classes
11th grade	It was alright. There was a benefit of being able to cheat but you missed out on proper social interactions with your friends and teachers.	Almost none. Kinda wack because no one wanted to turn on their cameras.	Worse because I realized how much I missed talking to people in person.	It was useful because I met my best friends - online tools that helped me cheat. Socratic, Brainly, Google, Sparknotes, and Resoomer.
11th grade	The wifi was inconsistent but there was more freetime	No social interaction	Better and worse	They were helpful but not as good as in person

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
11th grade	Was accessible, difficult to communicate to teachers through email or tutorials, but was more flexible	Little to none, breakout rooms were awkward, hard to talk with friends, but would text a lot in class	No, it was worse and better in some ways, I like it because there was more individual work time and teachers weren't forcing you to do work all period	Learned a lot, did well on my tests and quizzes
11th grade	it was accessible other than when I had wifi issues which happened often	very low; nobody would talk on zoom/can't make new friends	worse; i thought it would be much easier than in-person, but I could barely learn through virtual school/didn't understand much and lost motivation to finish assignments on time	not useful at all; barely learned anything and half of it was not applicable
11th grade	it was accessible to a medium extent in that while i did like online school since teachers were more lenient and i had better grades, we couldn't interact much with our friends or teachers. also there was many technical issues.	minimal, i didnt know many people in a lot of my online classes so i felt shy to talk to them.	it was exhausting but it was honestly not that bad. i got to spend more time with family and i got better grades.	they were useful. i learned a lot of things. however, i didnt get much hands-on experience to learn.
11th grade	It was very accessible	Little to none, because there was no need for any back and forth.	It was better for the fact of easier time management and more time for sleep.	It was relatively easy to understand the lessons being taught in each class.
10th grade	It was pretty accessible, but because of wifi issues I sometimes missed parts of the lesson.	I had a little bit of interaction because of zoom chat feature and texting/facetiming my friends.	It was better than I expected because I was able to sleep more and work at my own pace.	I learned mostly everything but it was hard to unmute and ask questions for clarification.
11th grade	Very accessible	Little to none	It was better	Not very useful
11th grade	pretty accessible for me	slim to none except breakout rooms that were generally rare	it was better than I expected because we still had regular classes and schedules	some of the classes I learned a lot but most I barely learned anything so it wasn't very useful

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online school?	Describe how much social interaction you had in online classes.	Was online school what you expected?	How useful were the online classes?
11th grade	Online school was mostly accessible. Sometimes it was not accessible such as when I had a test and my laptop would malfunction or my internet wouldn't work. Also, we couldn't do any labs in person which didn't help us.	I had very little social interaction in online classes. Teachers attempted to have us communicate through breakout rooms but it was awkward.	Worse than I expected, because of limited social interaction and mental health concerns.	I learned very little in online classes, I haven't retained most of my knowledge from online school.
10th grade	It was much less engaging but more convenient	Only over texts and occasionally at the park	No, it was worse as it was hard for me to focus or communicate with teachers	I did not learn much, and felt it was hard to understand the assignments
11th grade	very accessible	essentially none because my mom has health issues so we couldn't go out and see anyone that much...and I didn't get a phone until after sophomore year	yeah...but I was hoping more of my friends would be online too	pretty useful
11th grade	Drawbacks were internet connection cutting out sometimes but benefits were we could join the call wherever we were.	Almost none, the teacher would mostly interact with the in-person students.	Better and worse as my mental health and academic career plummeted but it was accessible.	They were useful for discussions, so to a small extent. I participated sometimes.
10th grade	There were technical difficulties such as WIFI. Although it was easier to attend in the morning.	I had minimal interaction. This is because it was kinda awkward, the only people I really talked to were my friends.	Worse, because I thought it would be the same thing but there was no interactions.	They were decent, because I learned a few things but forgot the rest.
10th grade	Benefits were that School was more flexible	I barely had any social interactions. I made friends but I felt alone	It was better because it was much easier mentally	I learned barely anything and it wasn't that applicable
10th grade	I liked it very much very straightforward	I always had to do with my parents everyday or even my teachers.	I loved it a lot because I got a lot of freedom with the time that I had left.	The online classes were useful and I learned because I had a lot of time and it helped me a lot.

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
11th grade	Very	Less	Yes	not much

Current Grade Level	How accessible was online	Describe how much social	Was online school what you	How useful were the online
11th grade	Kinda accessible	3	No worse	Not much
11th grade	I had access to multiple online sources, and I was able to still have a learning experience. However, when I had to do collaborative work, I had difficulties with it because I would not actually be there to help others. There was also lost of connection during the meetings which would lead to less class time to learn.	I would say social interaction was a 3. I was still able to communicate with others during the Zoom call. However, you can not really talk to others much during the meetings. It was hard to get more social interaction when you could only talk to others for a short period of time.	I expected online school to be better. This is because I would have a better sleep schedule and be able to go to school in the comforts of my own home. However, it turned out to be a disaster. It was hard to get a good education through online school. I could barely talk to other students. Finally, there was how my sleeping schedule actually got worse.	The online classes were a little useful. You could still do lessons for the teachers, but you could never see hands-on demonstrations or examples. The learning was also little including how applicable it was.
11th grade	It was very accessible, and drawbacks would be internet or Canvas issues	3, because we would do breakout rooms, but most people wouldn't wanna talk.	It was better than I expected it to be because I got to rest more and got better grades. It was still hard not seeing my friends, though.	They were useful, but we didn't learn as much as we did on a normal year. the learning wasn't really applicable, though.
11th grade	Very accessible	5, had some social interaction virtually through texts and calls but barely had any in person interaction.	It was better, as I got to use my time more freely	Some classes were helpful but generally way less effective than in person learning
10th grade	online school was pretty accessible apart from a few minor technological issues	3, because their was not too much communication in class.	yes it is what i expected and turned out better than i expected	I learned the same amount in online school because i had more time to finish the work